

Preconcentration and separation by imidazolylazo resin for copper and zinc determination in biological samples by AAS after microwave assisted treatment

Bhim Chandra Mondal, Debasis Das and Arabinda K. Das*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, India

E-mail : arabinda_k_das@yahoo.com Fax : 91-0342-64452

Manuscript received 28 July 2000, accepted 21 October 2000

The present paper describes a procedure for preconcentration, separation and sequential determination of trace amounts of copper and zinc by atomic absorption spectrometry. The proposed method is based on the solid phase extraction of the metal ion by imidazolylazo groups incorporated into a matrix of polystyrene-divinylbenzene. Parameters such as the amount of the resin, effect of pH, equilibration rate, sorption and desorption of metal ions, effect of diverse ions have been studied. The procedure has been applied to the determination of copper and zinc in several biological samples after their dissolution by microwave-assisted treatment. The method has a good accuracy.

Copper and zinc are amongst essential elements of life. Cu^{II} is present¹ in plastocyanin, a soluble copper containing electron transfer protein. It is also present in cytochrome oxidase, an electron transfer enzyme, in ceruloplasmin, a copper transporting glycoprotein in the blood of human and other vertebrates. Zn^{II} is present² in zinc proteases, a proteolytic enzyme. The catalytic enhancement of carbonic anhydrase is due to the action of Zn^{II} that is coordinated to the imidazole groups at three histidine residues in the enzyme. Again the active site of alcohol dehydrogenase contains Zn^{II} which is coordinated to the sulfur atoms of two cysteine residues and a histidine nitrogen atom. Copper/zinc ratio in biological samples is of great importance because it has significance not only in diagnosis of cancer³ and cardiac activity⁴ but also in determining optimal nutrition⁵. So the interference free determination of these metals is very essential.

Solid-phase extraction is now one of the interesting areas in analytical chemistry. Anchoring the active site to a solid support in a polymer matrix provides an immobilized active surface capable of selective and quantitative separation of cations from aqueous solutions. These solid-phase extraction systems can be used indefinitely without loss of the active ligating group. The developed procedure has been used to selectively remove and preconcentrate specific cations from the synthetic mixture of metal ions, environmental samples, recovery and purification of precious metals, separation of components from nuclear wastes⁶. Solid surfaces having heterocyclic donor sites has specific activity towards transition metal ions⁷. Imidazole and benzimidazole have biological importance and have

the ability to form complexes with a number of metal ions⁸. We have reported earlier the design of resins incorporating these groups in a polystyrene bed and used for the separation and preconcentration of class 'b' metal ions like Pd^{II} , Ag^{I} and Hg^{II} ⁹.

The present work reports the application of imidazolylazo resin for the preconcentration and separation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in biological samples after microwave-assisted digestion. The use of microwave oven for the dissolution of different type of environmental samples appear to be very attractive because it is very fast¹⁰. Procedure based on microwave-assisted digestion have been reported by several workers for the determination of copper and zinc in biological materials¹¹, but in these cases digestion conditions differ for different metals. Thus there is a strong need for a reliable analytical procedure for the determination of both these metals, particularly at very low level. Nevertheless, atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) is the general method of choice for copper and zinc detection due to high sensitivity of these elements.

Results and Discussion

Equilibration rates : The time required for 50% uptake of the maximum capacity for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was found to be 20 and 22 min, respectively. This shows that the resin is suitable for column operation under a low flow rate.

Sorption and desorption of metal ions : The sorption behaviour of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} on the resin (batch method) showed that the maximum capacity for Cu^{II} at pH 5.5–6.0 is 0.94 mmol g^{-1} and that for Zn^{II} at pH 4.5–5.0 is 0.60

mmol g⁻¹. The effect of different eluents on the desorption of metal ion is given in Table 1. Complete desorption of Cu^{II} took place with 25 ml of 1 mol dm⁻³ neutral 5-sulfosalicylic acid (SSA) solution.

Table 1. Desorption of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} by different eluents

Eluent	% Recovery	
	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
0.01 M HCl	37.5	40.0
0.1 M HCl	61.0	43.0
1.0 M HCl	93.8	103.4
2.0 M HCl	100.0	101.6
4.0 M HCl	100.0	100.0
1.0 M neutral SSA	100.0	0

Effect of diverse ions : Separation of 2 µg ml⁻¹ each of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} from several binary mixtures of various foreign ions in a sample volume of 50 ml at pH 5.0 and 5.5, respectively, were carried out. The presence of macro amounts of diverse metal ions like alkali and alkaline earth metal ions of the first transition series did not interfere except Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} which interfered to some extent (Table 2). This can be eliminated by adding little amount of thiocyanate to convert Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} into their anionic thiocyanato complex. Desorption of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was done with almost 100% recovery using suitable eluent as already described. Hence attempts were made to separate Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from binary synthetic mixture, various certified and common biological samples, viz. mussel tissue, chlorella, unpolished rice flour, rat liver, bird liver, fish liver etc.

Table 2. Separation of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} from several binary mixtures

Foreign ion*	% Recovery	
	Zn ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
	found	found
Hg ^{II}	56 (56)	82 (82)
Cd ^{II}	88 (88)	89 (89)
Co ^{II}	100 (100)	103 (103)
Cr ^{III}	100 (100)	100 (100)
Fe ^{III}	100 (100)	100 (100)
Ni ^{II}	101 (101)	102 (102)
Mn ^{II}	101 (101)	100 (100)
Mg ^{II}	100 (100)	100 (100)
Ba ^{II}	100 (100)	100 (100)
Na ^I	100 (100)	100 (100)
PO ₄ ³⁻	100 (100)	100 (100)
SO ₄ ²⁻	100 (100)	100 (100)
NO ₃	100 (100)	100 (100)

*In each case added foreign metal ion = 2000 µg.

The results of analysis of biological samples are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Separation and estimation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in biological samples

Sample (g)	Certified value µg g ⁻¹	Obtained value µg g ⁻¹	% Error
Mussel tissue (0.1760)	Cu : 7.96	Cu : 7.98	0.25
	Zn : 156.25	Zn : 158.63	0.24
Chlorella (0.3543)	Cu : 3.50	Cu : 3.23	7.71
	Zn : 20.50	Zn : 23.07	2.10
Rice flour unpolished (0.2528)	Cu : 3.50	Cu : 3.59	2.57
	Zn : 25.20	Zn : 25.49	1.15
Rat liver ^a (0.7426)		Cu : 0.75	
		Zn : 19.91	
Bird liver ^a (1.0505)		Cu : 0.097	
		Zn : 9.62	
Fish liver ^a (0.3486)		Cu : 2.5	
		Zn : 44.14	

^aWet tissue.

Conclusion : The result shows that resin containing imidazolylazo group is very selective for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}. This high selectivity may be due to the soft basic pyrrolic N-H of the imidazolylazo moiety; N-H plays the key role in binding and may be followed by chelation via azo-N. The resin thus has an immense potentiality for the effective preconcentration of trace copper and zinc from biological matrices. Microwave-assisted digestion followed by AAS allows reliable determination of these two metals in biological samples in which copper and zinc may be present at very low levels. The method proposed for the determination of copper : zinc ratio is rapid, simple and low cost.

Experimental

Atomic absorption spectrometric measurement was made with a GBC Avanta 908BT instrument with the following conditions : for copper, lamp current 4 mA, wavelength 324.7 nm, slit-width 0.5 nm; for zinc, lamp current 5 mA, wavelength 213.7 nm, slit-width 0.5 nm. pH was measured on a Systronics 362 pH meter. A domestic LG microwave oven with a 2450 MHz frequency magnetron and 650 W maximum power was employed to carry out the digestion of different samples assayed inside home-made polytetrafluoroethylene reactors, with 115 ml internal volume, 1 cm cell-wall thickness and hermetic screw caps.

Stock solutions of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of analytical grade zinc(II) sulfate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals) and copper(II) nitrate (B.D.H.) in double-distilled water and standardized with EDTA solution; working standard metal solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution. The following reference materials were analyzed : MA-M-2/TM mussel tissue (sample no. 325 of International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria, reference materials), NIES 3 chlorella and NIES 10 rice flour (both NIES certified reference materials from National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan

Environment Agency). All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Microwave-assisted digestion of samples : For complete dissolution of different types of biological materials, samples (176.0 mg to 1.0505 g) were treated hermetically sealed teflon reactors (115 ml) in the following way : the treatment of samples with 14 M HNO₃ (4 ml) in two steps (4 × 2 min) at irradiation power level of 360 W in both the cases, followed by a treatment with H₂O₂ for 4 min at 360 W. Finally, digestion at 360 W for 3 min ensured the total decomposition of these matrices. After digestion, each solution was diluted with water to a final volume of 25 ml.

Metal ion capacity as a function of pH : A batch technique was used, taking metal ion in excess to the resin. Capacity was determined in the pH range 1.0–6.0. To the imidazolylazo resin (100 mg), metal ion solution (excess) was added and pH of the solution was adjusted either by the addition of HCl or NaOH solution throughout the equilibrating period (24 h) until it remained constant at the desired level. Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} concentrations were determined by using atomic absorption spectrometer.

Studies of various eluting agents for desorption : The resin containing maximum absorbed metal ions were shaken with various eluting agents (30 ml), e.g. HCl of different strengths and neutral 5-sulfosalicylic acid (SSA) for 24 h. After filtration the amount of each of the metal ions in the filtrate was determined by AAS.

Column operation and effect of diverse ions : A 130 × 10 mm glass column was used. Air-dried resin (2 g) was immersed in double-distilled water and allowed to swell for 24 h. The column was then packed with fully swollen bed. The bed volume was 2.5 ml. The resin column was thoroughly washed with 10 bed volumes of HCl at appropriate pH.

The sorption and recovery characteristics for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in the presence of various metal ions were thoroughly studied. A 100 ml portion of the mixture of the test metal ion and foreign metal ions was allowed to flow through the resin column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. The metal ions not sorbed by the resin were completely washed out using hydrochloric acid solutions of pH 5.0 and 5.5, respectively, for Zn^{II} and Cu^{II}. Sorbed Cu^{II} was eluted completely with about 10 bed volume 1 mol dm⁻³ neutral 5-sulfosalicylic acid (SSA) and sorbed Zn^{II} was completely eluted with 25 ml of 1 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

Studies with resin blanks : To confirm that imidazolylazo group is responsible in metal ion sorption, the diazotized aminopolystyrene resin in sodium carbonate solution (pH 7) was boiled for several hours to replace the diazo group by the hydroxyl group. The Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ex-

change capacity of the resin was examined at pH 5.5 and 5.0, respectively, and found to be close to zero.

Applications : 100 µg each of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were mixed in double-distilled water (100 ml) and passed through the column loaded with imidazolylazo resin (2 g). Sorbed Cu^{II} was eluted completely with about 10 bed volumes of 1 mol dm⁻³ neutral 5-sulfosalicylic acid (SSA) and sorbed Zn^{II} was eluted completely with 25 ml of 1 mol dm⁻³ HCl. The result showed recovery of 96.5% Cu^{II} and 100% Zn^{II} from the binary mixtures of these two ions.

The biological samples were digested using microwave oven and analysed as above.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance (DSA). Thanks are also due to Prof. M. de la Guardia, Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of Valencia, Spain, for use of microwave oven while one of the authors (A.K.D.) visited Valencia.

References

1. A. L. Lelinger, D. L. Nelson and M. M. Cox, "Principle of Biochemistry", CBS Publishers, 1993.
2. L. Stryer, "Biochemistry", 4th. ed., W. H. Freeman, New York, 1995.
3. S. F. Bao, L. Zhao and F. L. Yang in "Metal Ions in Biology and Medicine", eds. P. Collery, P. Bratter, V. N. de Bratter, L. Khasanova and J. C. Etienne. John Libbey Eurotext, Montroge, France, 1998, Vol. 5.
4. S. Marchan, M. S. Davies, S. Flemming and H. D. Jones, *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A-Mol. Integr. Physiol.*, 1999, **123**, 89.
5. M. L. Failla, *Proc. Nutr. Soc.*, 1997, **58**, 497.
6. J. D. Lamb, R. M. Izatt, D. G. Ganick, J. S. Bradshaw and J. J. Christenson, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1981, **9**, 83; R. L. Bruening, B. J. Tarbet, K. E. Krakownik, M. L. Bruening, R. M. Izatt and J. S. Bradshaw, *Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 104; G. Wu, W. Jang, J. D. Lamb, J. S. Bradshaw and R. M. Izatt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 6538; R. M. Izatt, K. Pawlak, J. S. Bradshaw and R. L. Bruening, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 2529; J. S. Bradshaw and R. M. Izatt, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1997, **30**, 338.
7. J. P. Coolman, R. R. Gogne, J. Kouba and H. Lansberg-Wahren, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 6800; R. S. Drago and J. H. Gout, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 2019; P. Chattopadhyay, C. Sinha and D. K. Pal, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1997, **357**, 368.
8. A. R. Katritzky and C. W. Rees, *Comp. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1984, **5**, 347; R. A. Scott and D. M. Dooley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 4348.
9. D. Das, A. K. Das and C. Sinha, *Anal. Lett.*, 1999, **32**, 567; *Talanta*, 1999, **48**, 1013.
10. H. Matusiewicz and R. E. Sturgeon, *Prog. Anal. Spectrosc.*, 1989, **12**, 21; R. Chakraborty, A. K. Das, M. L. Cervera and M. de la Guardia, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1996, **355**, 99.
11. R. Demura, S. Tsukada and I. Yamamoto, *Eisei Kagaku*, 1985, **31**, 405; S. Baldwin, M. Deaker and W. Masher, *Analyst*, 1994, **119**, 1701.